

PIEZOELECTRIC RESONATORS LOADED WITH VISCOELASTIC AND NONUNIFORM MEDIA

Arthur Ballato

US Army Communications-Electronics Command
AMSEL-RD-CS, Fort Monmouth, NJ 07703-5201, USA
a.ballato@IEEE.org

Abstract - *This paper uses a simple, plane bulk acoustic wave model to discuss effects arising from changes occurring at the vibrating surfaces of a piezoelectric resonator, when exposed to coatings having various properties, as well as a variety of interfacial contact behaviors. The effect of air loading on the Q values of the three thickness modes of an SC-cut quartz resonator is computed for various pressures as an example of mode coupling by mechanical boundary conditions.*

INTRODUCTION

Piezoelectric resonators are used extensively as sensors for a wide variety of measurands [1]-[33], including mass loading [34]-[46], gases [47]-[48], liquids [49]-[69], mass and fluid loadings [70]-[71], viscoelastic/polymer coatings [72]-[79], suspensions/colloids [80]-[84], functionally gradient (non-homogeneous) materials and layers/stacks [85]-[88], and textured surfaces [89]-[91]. The ensuing changes are registered as changes in frequency, phase, and/or impedance level.

In some cases, such as temperature sensing, the bulk resonator material is affected. In other cases, e.g., quartz crystal microbalances, the frequency shift arises from changes occurring at, or near, the vibrating surfaces of the resonator. We consider this latter case. The thrust of the paper is to point out that the system should be treated as a whole: the piezoelectric resonator/actuator/transducer, the mechanical and electrical boundary conditions (BCs) specified at its surfaces, plus the immittance characteristics of the circuit into which the device is incorporated.

THE PIEZORESONATOR

We consider the case of a laterally unbounded piezoelectric plate supporting plane acoustic waves that have no lateral phase variations; these are the simple thickness modes [86]. The driving electric field may be either along or normal to the plate thickness, and the plate is mechanically loaded on both surfaces by a measurand. The resonator supports three modes, but the situation often dealt with in sensor applications is that where only one mode is piezoelectrically driven. For example, in quartz, the AT cut is a pure shear mode, excited by a field along the thickness, while in the X cut a thickness field drives the pure extensional (longitudinal) mode. When the plate is fashioned so that its surfaces are oblique to its crystallographic axes, all three modes are

driven in general, and should be taken into account, particularly for highly piezoelectric materials such as lithium niobate and lithium tantalate.

While the assumption of an unbounded plano-plano plate might seem unrealistic, work on finite and contoured plates with lateral distributions of motion shows that this one-dimensional idealization may very often convey the essence of the observed effects, particularly if the influences of piezoelectricity and circuit loading are properly taken into account [92]-[96].

Equivalent Circuits

Over the years, many equivalent circuits have been used to model the piezoresonator, and to describe its operation in using circuitry [97]-[112]. Detailed history and associated equivalent networks are found in [109]. The BVD lumped circuit evolved into more elaborate multi-mode, transmission-line networks that place the mechanical boundary loadings and piezoelectric excitation mechanism in series at the surfaces [109, Figs. 8, 10].

Piezoelectric Effect

The influence of piezoelectricity in a resonator is manifested in two distinct ways; the first is in so-called piezoelectric stiffening, whereby the elastic stiffnesses c^E governing acoustic wave speeds are augmented in a piezoelectric medium to effective stiffness values of the generic form $c = c^E/(1-k^2)$, where the k are dimensionless quantities known as piezocoupling coefficients.

The second place where piezoelectricity is manifest in resonators is in the driving mechanism, and is often considered only with respect to impedance level and insertion loss. Its influence can be subtler, however. Lawson [113], in his treatment of plate vibrations of a traction-free resonator, found that the "effective thickness" of the plate was greater than the geometrical thickness, and varied with mode and overtone. This is due to the electrical boundary conditions (BCs). Tiersten's exact solution of this problem [114] showed that all three modes are coupled at the boundaries by piezoelectricity. We will see in the SC-cut example below, an instance where mechanical BCs additionally couple all three modes. Mode coupling by these mechanisms must be taken into account for high precision and consistent analyses of sensor behavior, particularly with materials having strong piezocoupling.

MECHANICAL SURFACE LOADINGS

Mass deposited uniformly on the surface of a piezoelectric plate resonator lowers its frequency [34]-[46]; the quartz microbalance is based on this principle. This assumes that the mass is in welded contact with the resonator surface, and is represented solely by its inertial character. Dybwad found [115], however, that a microscopic gold sphere lightly dropped on the gold electrode of a thickness shear resonator plate caused the frequency to increase. He modeled the situation as one where the mass of the sphere was attached to the resonator surface by a spring. That is, the attached system possesses both inertial and elastic properties. It may be shown that, depending on the parameters involved, the frequency observed may either increase or decrease from the unloaded value. Onoe showed that, in certain instances, electrode mass increased the frequency of contour mode quartz resonators [116]. Mass and electrode stress have been implicated in a number of linear and nonlinear effects [117]-[120].

SOLID-FLUID INTERFACES

Lord Rayleigh, commenting on Stokes' treatment of fluid viscosity, wrote [47, §347]: "The velocity of the fluid in contact with the plane is usually assumed to be the same as that of the plane itself on the apparently sufficient ground that the contrary would imply an infinitely greater smoothness of the fluid with respect to the solid than with respect to itself." We assume this BC.

Ideal Fluid

An unbounded ideal fluid in intimate contact with a resonator surface will present to the surface a short circuit for shear waves, and a resistance to longitudinal motion of $R_\ell = A\rho v_\ell$, with A the cross-sectional area, ρ the fluid mass density, and v_ℓ the longitudinal acoustic velocity.

Newtonian Fluid

An unbounded Newtonian fluid (i.e., a fluid with shear viscosity, η) in intimate contact with a resonator surface presents to the surface both shear and longitudinal impedances. Shear impedance is $Z_s = A\sqrt{j\omega\eta\rho} = R_s + j\omega L_s$; R_s represents shear dissipation, and L_s entrained mass loading. Penetration depth is $\delta = \lambda/2\pi = \sqrt{2\eta/\rho\omega}$. Longitudinal impedance consists of $R_\ell = A\rho v_\ell$, plus a small reactance representing wave attenuation.

Viscoelastic Lumped Models

Often lumped circuit models can be used to represent viscoelastic materials [72]. Representative networks are shown in Fig. 1 (linear materials) and Fig. 2 (nonlinear materials). The nonlinear resistors of Fig. 2, representing dry friction, may themselves be represented as linear resistors in series with two back-biased diodes in parallel.

Lubricated Surfaces

Cady [121, §364, pp. 462-463] mentions reduction of friction between an extensional mode (X-cut) quartz plate and a solid surface apparently due to an entrapped layer of air. References [122]-[125] discuss other considerations of lubrication and slip at boundaries.

Fig. 1. Linear, viscoelastic lumped circuit models. Capacitors are analogous to springs; resistors are analogous to dashpots.

GENERAL MECHANICAL BCs

One must generally specify conditions on the three components of stress and three components of velocity at surface interfaces. Assuming plate thickness along the X_2 axis, one must specify conditions on T_{12} , T_{22} , and T_{23} , plus v_1 , v_2 , and v_3 . Welded conditions correspond to continuity of all six quantities; blockage corresponds to $v_1 = v_2 = v_3 = 0$; transverse slippage corresponds to continuity of T_{22} , and $T_{12} = T_{23} = 0$, etc. In general, the six boundary variables are related by an immittance matrix that may be expressed in terms equivalent to those descriptions used in network theory: homogeneous forms of impedance [z] and admittance [y]; mixed forms, [g], [h]; scattering [s]; [ABCD], etc.

Textured Interfaces

With the advent of micro/nano technologies [126]-[128], one is led to consider the possibilities of manufacturing interfaces that impose desired BCs. These may be made in a self-organizing manner [129]. Figure 3 gives two examples.

Surface Particles and Bonds

Particles on the surface of a resonator have been a manufacturer's bane for many years, and have been shown to be the cause of various anomalies, e.g., drive level dependence [120]. Loosely applied particles such as lycopodium powder [121, §366, pp. 463-465] can move about from resonator motion; lightly attached particles, such as Dybwad's microspheres [115], might possibly detach with sufficiently

high levels of drive. The breaking of molecular bonds by resonator motion, on the other hand, is another matter. One may estimate the possibility of expulsion of attached surface molecules by considering the force required to rupture a bond. Strength of the covalent C-C bond is ~ 10 nN/bond; for other types of bond the range is ~ 1 to 10 nN/bond [126]. As an example, we take the rather extreme case of an unloaded thin-film vibrator in resonance at 220 MHz with piezocoupling of 51%, R_1C_1 time constant of 100 femto-seconds (ten times that of quartz), and 1% surface strain [130]. Amplitude is limited solely by internal friction; the resonator power dissipation is ~ 30 W/mm², has surface amplitude of ~ 440 Å, and surface acceleration of $\sim 8.5E+10$ m/s². A carbon atom of mass 12 amu $\sim 2E-26$ kg on the resonator surface experiences a force of $\sim 1.7E-15$ N. This is about six million times less than the classical force required to rupture a bond; consequently, the probability of this happening is vanishingly small.

MODE COUPLING BY A FLUID

In the discussion of solid-fluid interfaces above, expressions are given for the longitudinal and shear impedances presented to the solid resonator surface. The usual sensor configuration consists of a resonator/transducer utilizing a single acoustic mode. Moreover, it is a pure mode, having motion strictly along the thickness direction (e.g., X-cut quartz or Z-cut ZnO), or strictly normal to the thickness (e.g., AT-cut quartz or X-cut lithium niobate).

Fig. 2. Nonlinear, viscoelastic lumped circuit models. Nonlinear resistors are analogous to dry friction.

In these instances, it is only necessary to consider one of the fluid impedances. In the more general situation where a doubly rotated resonator orientation is utilized [64], as with the SC-cut of quartz, the solid surface executes resonant motions that are oblique to its normal at each of the three modes (and their overtones). Treating this case requires that both fluid impedances be incorporated; in [64] this was done using the simple, lumped BVD network. It is instructive to do a more involved example, which shows explicitly the mode coupling that takes place via mechanical BCs.

AIR-LOADED SC-CUT QUARTZ

The SC quartz cut is doubly rotated, meaning that the plate axes are oblique to the crystallographic axes. Its properties, and corresponding numerical data are given in [86]. We take the right-handed orthogonal plate (laboratory) coordinates as follows: X_1 along the digonal crystal axis, and X_2 along the plate thickness. In this cut, all three simple thickness modes are excited by an electric field in the X_2 direction. The appropriate electrical equivalent circuit is that given in [109, Fig. 10]. Appearing at the six mechanical ports, however, are the mechanical variables of stress and velocity referred to the normal (internal, eigenfunction) coordinates within the plate. The connection between these systems is represented in network form by the ideal transformer circuit given in [109, Fig. 15], attached to each plate surface. Algebraically, the impedance presented at each interface in the laboratory coordinates is converted by a similarity transformation to impedance referred to the normal (internal) coordinates. The transformation is

$$Z_{\text{internal}} = \beta^T \cdot Z_{\text{laboratory}} \cdot \beta,$$

where β is the modal matrix.

Immersion in Air Ambient

For simplicity rather than necessity, we assume that both surfaces of the SC-cut quartz plate are exposed to unbounded reservoirs of air at the same pressure. The equal surface loadings render the configuration symmetric about the midsection of the crystal, and permit bisection of the network [131]-[133]. The result is shown in Fig. 4. “Analyte modal immittances” are, in this case, the longitudinal (L) and shear ($S_1 = S_2$) impedances of air, considered as a Newtonian fluid. Three modal acoustic transmission lines (TLs) represent quasi-longitudinal (“a” mode), fast quasi-shear (“b” mode), and slow quasi-shear (“c” mode) motions. The TL lengths equal the geometrical half-thickness of the plate, with doubled acoustic admittances, due to bisection. The three n_m are piezoelectric transformer turns ratios ($m = a, b, \text{ or } c$ mode), permitting the voltage impressed at the electrical port to drive the resonator. Values n_m are proportional to the corresponding piezocoupling factors of the modes [86].

Slippery Dovetail Array

$$T_{22}, T_{23} \text{ Continuous}$$

$$T_{12} = 0$$

Dovetails may be at an angle in x_1 - x_3 plane

Slippery Mortise & Tenon Array

$$T_{12}, T_{23} \text{ Continuous}$$

$$T_{22} = 0$$

Fig. 3. Examples of textured interfaces, as might be realized by micromachining, and other microtechnology processes.

Fluid Impedance Matrix

For the present case, $Z_{\text{laboratory}}$ is Z_{fluid} , where

$$Z_{\text{fluid}} = \begin{pmatrix} Z_{\text{shear}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & Z_{\text{long}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Z_{\text{shear}} \end{pmatrix},$$

with $Z_{\text{shear}} = Z_s = A\sqrt{j\omega\eta\rho}$, and $Z_{\text{long}} = R_\ell = A\rho v_\ell$. The modal matrix β is

$$\beta = \begin{pmatrix} \beta_1^{(c)} & \beta_1^{(a)} & \beta_1^{(b)} \\ \beta_2^{(c)} & \beta_2^{(a)} & \beta_2^{(b)} \\ \beta_3^{(c)} & \beta_3^{(a)} & \beta_3^{(b)} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Superscripts denote modes; mode "c", the slow quasi-shear, has particle motion predominantly along the X_1 axis, etc. Although Z_{fluid} is diagonal, the similarity transformation with β produces a symmetric impedance matrix in the normal coordinate system that contains no zeros. For the SC-cut of quartz, β has the following numerical values:

$$\beta = \begin{pmatrix} +0.9605 & +0.2217 & -0.1681 \\ -0.2364 & +0.9689 & -0.0730 \\ +0.1467 & +0.1099 & +0.9831 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Acoustic Properties of Air

Table 1 contains values of pertinent acoustic properties of air at 300° K, at three pressures [134]-[135]. Penetration depth δ is for 10 MHz, the nominal frequency of the SC-cut c-mode example. Rayleigh [47, p. 313] remarks: "Both by theory and experiment the remarkable conclusion has been established that within wide limits the force [viscosity] is independent of the density of the gas. For air at θ° Centigrade Maxwell found $[\eta] = .0001878 (1 + .00366 \theta) \dots$ ". The modern MKS value is listed.

Table 1. Acoustic Properties of Air at 300 ° K

Pressure	Density	Velocity	Viscosity	Depth δ
(atm)	(kg/m ³)	(m/s)	(μ Pa-s)	(μ m)
0.1	0.11767	347.23		2.24
1.0	1.1769	347.33	18.464	0.707
10	11.799	348.49		0.223

Resonator Input Admittance

The impedance matrix of air is referred back to the normal coordinate frame via

$$Z_{\text{normal}} = \beta^T \cdot Z_{\text{fluid}} \cdot \beta,$$

attached to the modal TLs as in Fig. 4, and the result is solved for the input admittance at the electrical port. Input

Fig. 4. Doubly rotated quartz resonator used as a fluid sensor.

admittance, normalized to that of the resonator static capacitance C_0 at $f_{oc} = 10$ MHz, is graphed in Fig. 5 for three values of ambient pressure. The frequency scale is normalized to c-mode frequency f_{oc} . Resonances become increasingly blunted with pressure. Similar curves obtain for the other modes, but the effect is particularly marked for the quasi-longitudinal "a" mode, as is to be expected. When reflecting boundaries, parallel to the plate surfaces, replace the unbounded reservoirs, the resulting finite layers of air form additional resonant structures and yield modulations of the curves in Fig. 5 [69].

Table 2 provides the quality factors Q_m for each mode of the SC-cut quartz plate, assuming that loss arises solely from air loading. Also given are the intrinsic Q values for an unloaded resonator, assuming acoustic viscosity in quartz [86], and the fundamental modal frequencies; the plate is 0.1797 mm thick.

Table 2. Quality Factors of Air-Loaded SC-cut Quartz

Pressure	Q_a	Q_b	Q_c
(atm) ↓	E+3	E+3	E+3
0.1	209	524	370
1	20.9	162	89.3
10	2.12	44.0	14.1
$Q_{intrinsic} \rightarrow$	805	2,278	1,360
f_{om} (MHz) →	18.820	11.001	10.000

CONCLUSIONS

Optimum performance of a sensor, actuator, or transducer is achieved when it is treated, along with using circuitry, as a complete system. To do this, the interplay of various effects must be taken into account. This paper has discussed a number of these, relating to piezoelectricity, equivalent circuits, boundary effects, and mode coupling. An air-loaded SC-cut quartz plate resonator is treated as an example.

REFERENCES

- [1] V. Mecea and R. V. Bucur, "The mechanism of the interaction of thin films with resonating quartz crystal substrates: The energy transfer model," *Thin Solid Films*, vol. 60, pp. 73-84, 1979.
- [2] E. Benes, "Improved quartz crystal microbalance technique," *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 56, no. 3, pp. 608-626, 1 August 1984.
- [3] H. Nowotny and E. Benes, "General one-dimensional treatment of the layered piezoelectric resonator with two electrodes," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 82, no. 2, pp. 513-521, August 1987.
- [4] T. Nakamoto and T. Moriizumi, "A theory of a quartz crystal microbalance based upon a Mason equivalent circuit," *Jap. J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 29, no. 5, pp. 963-969, May 1990.
- [5] H. Nowotny, E. Benes, and M. Schmid, "Layered piezoelectric resonators with an arbitrary number of electrodes (general one-dimensional treatment)," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 90, no. 3, pp. 1238-1245, September 1991.

Fig. 5. Normalized admittance versus normalized frequency in the vicinity of c-mode resonance for an SC-cut quartz plate of 10 MHz nominal frequency for three values of ambient air loading pressure.

- [6] G. Hayward, "Viscous interaction with oscillating piezoelectric quartz crystals," *Analytica Chimica Acta*, vol. 264, pp. 23-30, 1992.
- [7] E. A. Klavetter, S. J. Martin, and K. O. Wessendorf, "Monitoring jet fuel thermal stability using a quartz crystal microbalance," *Energy & Fuels*, vol. 7, no. 5, pp. 582-588, 1993.
- [8] M. A. Grundy, W. E. Bolek, W. T. Coakley, and E. Benes, "Rapid agglutination testing in an ultrasonic standing wave," *J. Immunol. Methods*, vol. 165, pp. 47-57, 1993.
- [9] H. Drobe, A. Leidl, M. Rost, and I. Ruge, "Acoustic sensors based on surface-localized HPSWs for measurements in liquids," *Sensors and Actuators*, vol. A 37-38, pp. 141-148, 1993.
- [10] V. M. Mecea, "Loaded vibrating quartz sensors," *Sensors and Actuators*, vol. A40, pp. 1-27, 1994.
- [11] V. M. Mecea, "Vibrating piezoelectric sensors," *Sensors and Actuators*, vol. A41-42, pp. 630-637, 1994.
- [12] G. L. Hayward and G. Z. Chu, "Simultaneous measurement of mass and viscosity using piezoelectric quartz crystals in liquid media," *Analytica Chimica Acta*, vol. 288, pp. 179-185, 1994.
- [13] R. W. Cernosek, S. J. Martin, K. O. Wessendorf, M. D. Terry, and A. N. Rumpf, "Quartz resonator fluid monitors for vehicle applications," *Proc. Sensors Expo*, pp. 527-539, Cleveland, OH, September 1994.
- [14] T. W. Schneider and S. J. Martin, "Influence of compressional wave generation on thickness-shear mode resonator response in a fluid," *Anal. Chem.*, vol. 67, no. 18, pp. 3324-3335, September 15, 1995.
- [15] T. W. Schneider, G. C. Frye, S. J. Martin, and J. J. Spates, "Investigation of the quartz resonator as an industrial cleaning monitor," *Analytica Chimica Acta*, vol. 309, pp. 53-62, 1995.
- [16] E. Benes, M. Gröschl, W. Burger, and M. Schmid, "Sensors based on piezoelectric resonators," *Sensors and Actuators*, vol. A48, pp. 1-21, 1995.
- [17] J. R. Vig and R. L. Filler, "Chemical sensor based on quartz microresonators," *J. Microelectromech. Syst.*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 138-140, June 1996.
- [18] C. Zhang and G. Feng, "Contributions of amplitude measurement in QCM sensors," *IEEE Trans. Ultrason., Ferroelect., Freq. Contr.*, vol. 43, no. 5, pp. 942-947, September 1996.
- [19] V. M. Mecea, J. O. Carlsson, and R. V. Bucur, "Extensions of the quartz-crystal-microbalance technique," *Sensors and Actuators*, vol. A53, pp. 371-378, 1996.
- [20] E. Benes, M. Gröschl, F. Seifert, and A. Pohl, "Comparison between BAW and SAW sensor principles," *IEEE Intl. Freq. Contr. Symp. Proc.*, pp. 5-20, Orlando, FL, May 1997.
- [21] J. M. Hammond, R. M. Lec, X. J. Zhang, D. G. Libby and L. A. Prager, "An acoustic automotive engine oil quality sensor," *IEEE Intl. Freq. Control Symp. Proc.*, pp. 72-80, Orlando, FL, May, 1997.
- [22] R. Thalhammer, S. Braun, B. Devcic-Kuhar, M. Gröschl, F. Trampler, E. Benes, H. Nowotny, M. Kostal, M. Hruskovic, and J. Hrbik, "Viscosity sensor based upon an angular momentum compensated piezoelectric thickness shear sandwich resonator," *IEEE Intl. Freq. Contr. Symp. Proc.*, pp. 105-113, Orlando, FL, May 1997.
- [23] C. Behling, R. Lucklum, and P. Hauptmann, "Direct method for shear moduli calculation from quartz crystal resonator measurements," *IEEE Intl. Freq. Contr. Symp. Proc.*, pp. 823-830, Pasadena, CA, May 1998.
- [24] E. Benes, M. Gröschl, F. Seifert, and A. Pohl, "Comparison between BAW and SAW sensor principles," *IEEE Trans. Ultrason., Ferroelect., Freq. Contr.*, vol. 45, no. 5, pp. 1314-1330, September 1998.
- [25] R. Thalhammer, S. Braun, B. Devcic-Kuhar, M. Gröschl, F. Trampler, E. Benes, H. Nowotny, and M. Kostal, "Viscosity sensor utilizing a piezoelectric thickness shear sandwich resonator," *IEEE Trans. Ultrason., Ferroelect., Freq. Contr.*, vol. 45, no. 5, pp. 1331-1340, September 1998.
- [26] A. Menon, R. Zhou, and F. Josse, "Coated-quartz crystal resonator (QCR) sensors for on-line detection of organic contaminants in water," *IEEE Trans. Ultrason., Ferroelect., Freq. Contr.*, vol. 45, no. 5, pp. 1416-1426, September 1998.
- [27] C. Behling, R. Lucklum, and P. Hauptmann, "Fast three-step method for shear moduli calculation from quartz crystal resonator measurements," *IEEE Trans. Ultrason., Ferroelect., Freq. Contr.*, vol. 46, no. 6, pp. 1431-1438, November 1999.
- [28] R. Lucklum, C. Behling, and P. Hauptmann, "Signal amplification with multilayer arrangements on chemical quartz-crystal-resonator-sensors," *Proc. Joint Meeting of the 13th European Freq. and Time Forum and the 1999 IEEE Intl. Freq. Control Symp.*, pp. 987-990, Besançon, April 1999 and *IEEE Trans. Ultrason., Ferroelect., Freq. Contr.*, vol. 47, no. 5, pp. 1246-1252, September 2000.
- [29] P. Hauptmann, R. Borngraeber, J. Schroeder, and J. Auge, "Application of novel sensor electronics for quartz resonators in artificial tongue," *IEEE Intl. Freq. Contr. Symp. Proc.*, pp. 100-105, Kansas City, MO, June 2000.
- [30] A. Arnau, T. Sogorb, and Y. Jiménez, "A new method for continuous monitoring of series resonance frequency and simple determination of motional impedance parameters for loaded quartz-crystal resonators," *IEEE Trans. Ultrason., Ferroelect., Freq. Contr.*, vol. 48, no. 2, pp. 617-623, March 2001.
- [31] R. Lucklum and P. Hauptmann, "Thin film shear modulus determination with quartz crystal resonators: A review," *IEEE Intl. Freq. Contr. Symp. Proc.*, pp. 408-418, Seattle, WA, June 2001.
- [32] R. M. Lec, "Piezoelectric biosensors: Recent advances and applications," *IEEE Intl. Freq. Contr. Symp. Proc.*, pp. 419-429, Seattle, WA, June 2001.
- [33] R. Lucklum, P. Hauptmann, and R. W. Cernosek, "Thin film material properties with quartz crystal resona-

- tors," IEEE Intl. Freq. Contr. Symp. Proc., pp. 542-550, Seattle, WA, June 2001.
- [34] G. Sauerbrey, "Verwendung von Schwingquarzen zur Wägung dünner Schichten und zur Mikrowägung," *Z. Physik*, vol. 155, pp. 206-222, 1959.
- [35] J. G. Miller and D. I. Bolef, "Sensitivity enhancement by the use of acoustic resonators in cw ultrasonic spectroscopy," *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 39, no. 10, pp. 4589-4593, September 1968.
- [36] J. G. Miller and D. I. Bolef, "Acoustic wave analysis of the operation of quartz-crystal film-thickness monitors," *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 39, pp. 5815-5816, 1968.
- [37] C. -S. Lu and O. Lewis, "Investigation of film-thickness determination by oscillating quartz resonators with large mass load," *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 43, no. 11, pp. 4385-4390, November 1972.
- [38] A. Ballato and T. Lukaszek, "Mass effects on crystal resonators with arbitrary piezo-coupling," *Proc. 27th Annual Freq. Control Symp.*, pp. 20-29, Cherry Hill, NJ, June 1973.
- [39] A. Ballato and T. Lukaszek, "Mass-loading of thickness-excited crystal resonators having arbitrary piezo-coupling," *IEEE Trans. Sonics Ultrason.*, vol. SU-21, no. 4, pp. 269-274, October 1974.
- [40] E. C. van Ballegooijen, "Simultaneous mass and temperature determination using a single quartz wafer: An optimized crystal cut," *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 50, no. 1, pp. 91-101, January 1979.
- [41] Applications of Piezoelectric Quartz Crystal Microbalances (C. Lu and A. W. Czanderna, Eds.), Volume 7 of Methods and Phenomena: Their Applications in Science and Technology, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1984.
- [42] W. Stöckel and R. Schumacher, "In situ microweighing at the junction metal/electrolyte," *Ber. Bunsenges. Phys. Chem.*, vol. 91, pp. 345-349, 1987.
- [43] P. J. Cumpson and M. P. Seah, "The quartz crystal microbalance; radial/polar dependence of mass sensitivity both on and off the electrode," *Meas. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 1, pp. 544-555, 1990.
- [44] A. S. Way, "Quartz resonator techniques for simultaneous measurement of areal mass density, lateral stress, and temperature in thin films," *Vacuum*, vol. 44, nos. 3-4, pp. 385-388, 1993.
- [45] R. V. Bucur, J. -O. Carlsson, and V. M. Mecea, "Quartz-crystal mass sensors with glued foil electrodes," *Sensors and Actuators*, vol. B37, pp. 91-95, November 1996.
- [46] M. Nakazawa, "Analysis of thickness dependence on electrical equivalent circuit model for AT-cut resonators," *IEEE Intl. Ultrasonics Symp. Proc.*, pp. 925-930, Sendai, Japan, October 1998.
- [47] J. W. S. Rayleigh, *The Theory of Sound*, Vol. 2, second revised edition, (1896), Dover, New York, 1945.
- [48] R. Lucklum, B. Henning, P. Hauptmann, K. D. Schierbaum, S. Vaihinger, and W. Göpel, "Quartz microbalance sensors for gas detection," *Sensors and Actuators*, vol. A25-27, pp. 705-710, 1991.
- [49] W. P. Mason, "Viscosity and shear elasticity measurements of liquids by means of shear vibrating crystals," *J. Colloid Sci.*, vol. 3, pp. 147-162, 1948.
- [50] S. Bruckenstein and M. Shay, "Experimental aspects of use of the quartz crystal microbalance in solution," *Electrochimica Acta*, vol. 30, no. 10, pp. 1295-1300, 1985.
- [51] K. K. Kanazawa and J. G. Gordon II, "The oscillation frequency of a quartz resonator in contact with a liquid," *Analytica Chimica Acta*, vol. 175, pp. 99-105, 1985.
- [52] K. K. Kanazawa and J. G. Gordon II, "Frequency of a quartz microbalance in contact with liquid," *Anal. Chem.*, vol. 57, pp. 1771-1772, 1985.
- [53] H. Muramatsu, E. Tamiya, and I. Karube, "Computation of equivalent circuit parameters of quartz crystals in contact with liquids and study of liquid properties," *Anal. Chem.*, vol. 60, no. 19, pp. 2142-2146, October 1, 1988.
- [54] B. A. Martin and H. E. Hager, "Velocity profile on quartz crystals oscillating in liquids," *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 65, no. 7, pp. 2630-2635, 1 April 1989.
- [55] E. Benes, M. Schmid, and V. Kravchenko, "Vibration modes of mass-loaded planoconvex quartz crystal resonators," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 90, no. 2, part 1, pp. 700-706, August 1991.
- [56] W. Wei, Z. Mo, and S. Yao, "Multi-component analysis in solution using piezoelectric quartz sensors," *Analytica Chimica Acta*, vol. 251, pp. 143-148, 1991.
- [57] Z. Lin, C. M. Yip, I. S. Joseph, and M. D. Ward, "Operation of an ultrasensitive 30-MHz quartz crystal microbalance in liquids," *Anal. Chem.*, vol. 65, no. 11, pp. 1546-1551, June 11, 1993.
- [58] S. J. Martin, G. C. Frye, and K. O. Wissendorf, "Sensing liquid properties with thickness-shear mode resonators," *Sensors and Actuators*, vol. A44, pp. 209-218, 1994.
- [59] Z. Lin and M. D. Ward, "The role of longitudinal waves in quartz crystal microbalance applications in liquids," *Anal. Chem.*, vol. 67, no. 4, pp. 685-693, February 15, 1995.
- [60] M. Rodahl, F. Höök, A. Krozer, P. Brzezinski, and B. Kasemo, "Quartz crystal microbalance setup for frequency and Q-factor measurements in gaseous and liquid environments," *Rev. Sci. Instrum.*, vol. 66., no. 7, pp. 3924-3930, July 1995.
- [61] B. Devcic-Kuhar, D. Harrer, R. Thalhammer, M. Gröschl, E. Benes, H. Nowotny, and F. Trampler, "Three layer thickness extensional mode piezoelectric resonator for determining density and sound velocity of liquids," *IEEE Intl. Freq. Contr. Symp. Proc.*, pp. 81-89, Orlando, FL, May 1997.
- [62] M. Thompson and G. L. Hayward, "Mass response of the thickness-shear mode acoustic wave sensor in liquids as a central misleading dogma," *IEEE Intl. Freq. Control Symp. Proc.*, pp. 114-119, Orlando, FL, May, 1997.

- [63] S. J. Martin, J. J. Spates, K. O. Wessendorf, T. W. Schneider, and R. C. Huber, "Resonator/oscillator response to liquid loading," *Anal. Chem.*, vol. 69, no. 11, pp. 2050-2054, June 1, 1997.
- [64] Y. Kim, J. R. Vig, and A. Ballato, "Sensing the properties of liquids with doubly rotated resonators," *IEEE Intl. Freq. Contr. Symp. Proc.*, pp. 660-666, Pasadena, CA, May 1998.
- [65] A. Püttner and P. Hauptmann, "Ultrasonic density sensor for liquids," *IEEE Intl. Ultrason. Symp. Proc.*, pp. 497-500, Sendai, Japan, October 1998.
- [66] R. Thalhammer, B. Devcic-Kuhar, D. Harrer, F. Trampler, E. Benes, M. Gröschl, and H. Nowotny, "Piezoelectric sandwich resonator for sensing viscosity, sound speed, and density of liquids," 194th Meeting of The Electrochemical Society, Z1 – Acoustic Wave-based Sensors, Boston, MA, November 1998, 1p.
- [67] R. Borngraeber, J. Schroeder, R. Lucklum, and P. Hauptmann, "Is an oscillator based measurement adequate in a liquid environment?," *IEEE Intl. Freq. Contr. Symp. Proc.*, pp. 443-448, Seattle, WA, June 2001.
- [68] C. Zhang and J. Vetelino, "A bulk acoustic wave resonator for sensing liquid electrical property changes," *IEEE Intl. Freq. Contr. Symp. Proc.*, pp. 535-541, Seattle, WA, June 2001.
- [69] P. C. Y. Lee and R. Huang, "Effects of a liquid layer on thickness-shear vibrations of rectangular AT-cut quartz plates," *IEEE Trans. Ultrason., Ferroelect., Freq. Contr.*, vol. 49, no. 5, pp. 604-611, May 2002.
- [70] S. J. Martin, V. E. Granstaff, and G. C. Frye, "Characterization of a quartz crystal microbalance with simultaneous mass and liquid loading," *Anal. Chem.*, vol. 63, no. 20, pp. 2272-2281, October 15, 1991.
- [71] C. Zhang, F. Feng, and S. Sui, "A new approach to the development of quartz crystal sensors distinguishing between mass loading and liquid damping," *IEEE Trans. Instrum. Meas.*, vol. 47, no. 5, pp. 1234-1238, October 1998.
- [72] W. C. Sperry, "Rheological-model concept," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 36, no. 2, pp. 376-385, February 1964.
- [73] R. A. Crane and G. Fischer, "Analysis of a quartz crystal microbalance with coatings of finite viscosity," *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.*, vol. 12, pp. 2019-2026, 1979.
- [74] H. Ohigashi, T. Itoh, K. Kimura, T. Nakanishi, and M. Suzuki, "Analysis of frequency response characteristics of polymer ultrasonic transducers," *Japanese J. Appl. Physics*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 354-360, March 1988.
- [75] C. E. Reed, K. K. Kanazawa, and J. H. Kaufman, "Physical description of a viscoelastically loaded AT-cut quartz resonator," *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 68, no. 5, pp. 1993-2001, 1 September 1990.
- [76] B. Hartmann, G. F. Lee, and J. D. Lee, "Loss factor height and width limits for polymer relaxations," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 95, no. 1, pp. 226-233, January 1994.
- [77] S. J. Martin, G. C. Frye, and S. D. Senturia, "Dynamics and response of polymer-coated surface acoustic wave devices: Effect of viscoelastic properties and film resonance," *Anal. Chem.*, vol. 66, no. 14, pp. 2201-2219, July 15, 1994.
- [78] J. M. Carcione, "On energy definition in electromagnetism: An analogy with viscoelasticity," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 105, no. 2, part 1, pp. 626-632, February 1999.
- [79] D. K. Gramotnev and M. L. Mather, "Anomalous absorption of bulk shear acoustic waves by an ultra-thin layer of a non-Newtonian fluid," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 106, no. 5, pp. 2552-2559, November 1999.
- [80] M. Gröschl, "Ultrasonic separation of suspended particles – Part I: Fundamentals," *Acta Acustica*, vol. 84, pp. 432-447, 1998.
- [81] M. Gröschl, "Ultrasonic separation of suspended particles – Part II: Design and operation of separation devices," *Acta Acustica*, vol. 84, pp. 632-642, 1998.
- [82] M. Gröschl, W. Burger, B. Handl, O. Doblhoff-Dier, T. Gaida, and C. Schmatz, "Ultrasonic separation of suspended particles – Part III: Application in biotechnology," *Acta Acustica*, vol. 84, pp. 815-822, 1998.
- [83] F. T. Schultz, Y. Lu, and H. N. G. Wadley, "Ultrasonic propagation in metal powder-viscous liquid suspensions," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 103, no. 3, pp. 1361-1369, March 1998.
- [84] R. M. Lec and J. Sorial, "The study of colloidal systems with TSM piezoelectric sensors," *IEEE Intl. Freq. Contr. Symp. Proc.*, pp. 838-845, Seattle, WA, June 2001.
- [85] M. Onoe and K. Okada, "Analysis of contoured piezoelectric resonators vibrating in thickness-twist modes," *Proc. 23rd Annual Frequency Control Symp.*, pp. 26-38, Atlantic City, NJ, May 1969.
- [86] A. Ballato, "Doubly rotated thickness mode plate vibrators," In *Physical Acoustics: Principles and Methods*, (W. P. Mason and R. N. Thurston, Eds.) Vol. 13, Ch. 5, pp. 115-181, 1977. Academic Press, New York. ISBN 0-12-477913-1.
- [87] J. Ballato, R. Schwartz, and A. Ballato, "Network formalism for modeling functionally gradient piezoelectric plates and stacks and simulations of rainbow ceramic actuators," *IEEE Trans. Ultrason., Ferroelect., Freq. Contr.*, vol. 48, no. 2, pp. 462-476, March 2001.
- [88] R. Lucklum and P. Hauptmann, "Generalized acoustic parameters of non-homogeneous thin films," these proceedings.
- [89] S. J. Martin, K. O. Wessendorf, C. T. Gebert, G. C. Frye, R. W. Cernosek, L. Casaus, and M. A. Mitchell, "Measuring liquid properties with smooth- and textured-surface resonators," *IEEE Intl. Freq. Control Symp. Proc.*, pp. 603-608, Salt Lake City, UT, June, 1993.
- [90] S. J. Martin, G. C. Frye, A. J. Ricco, and S. D. Senturia, "Effect of surface roughness on the response of thickness-shear mode resonators in liquids," *Anal. Chem.*, vol. 65, no. 20, pp. 2910-2922, October 15, 1993.

- [91] C. Zhang, S. Schranz, R. Lucklum, and P. Hauptmann, "Mass effects of quartz resonant sensors with different surface microstructures in liquids," *IEEE Trans. Ultrason., Ferroelect., Freq. Contr.*, vol. 45, no. 5, pp. 1204-1210, September 1998.
- [92] L. Wimmer, S. Hertl, J. Hemetsberger, and E. Benes, "New method of measuring vibration amplitudes of quartz crystals," *Rev. Sci. Instrum.*, vol. 55, no. 4, pp. 605-609, April 1984.
- [93] S. Hertl, L. Wimmer, and E. Benes, "Investigation of the amplitude distribution of AT-cut quartz crystals," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 78, no. 4, pp. 1337-1343, October 1985.
- [94] J. R. Vig and A. Ballato, "Comments about the effects on nonuniform mass loading on a quartz crystal microbalance," *IEEE Trans. Ultrason., Ferroelect., Freq. Contr.*, vol. 45, no. 5, pp. 1123-1124, September 1998.
- [95] H. Nowotny, N. Finger, E. Benes, and M. Gröschl, "Vibration modes of piezoelectric plates with small spatial thickness variation," *Proc. Joint Meeting 13th European Freq. and Time Forum and the 1999 IEEE Intl. Freq. Control Symp.*, pp. 501-504, Besançon, April 1999.
- [96] B. K. Sinha, "Doubly rotated contoured quartz resonators," *IEEE Trans. Ultrason., Ferroelect., Freq. Contr.*, vol. 48, no. 5, pp. 1162-1180, September 2001.
- [97] G. Arlt, "Resonance-antiresonance of conducting piezoelectric resonators," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 151-157, January 1965.
- [98] T. R. Meeker, "Thickness mode piezoelectric transducers," *Ultrasonics*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 26-36, January 1972.
- [99] M. Brunot, "Structures piézoélectriques à couches multiples," *Ann. Télécommunic.*, vol. 31, nos. 1-2, pp. 45-73, 1976.
- [100] M. Schmid, E. Benes, and R. Sedlaczek, "A computer-controlled system for the measurement of complete admittance spectra of piezoelectric resonators," *Meas. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 1, pp. 970-975, 1990.
- [101] M. Schmid, E. Benes, W. Burger, and V. Kravchenko, "Motional capacitance of layered piezoelectric thickness-mode resonators," *IEEE Trans. Ultrason., Ferroelect., Freq. Contr.*, vol. 38, no. 3, pp. 199-206, May 1991.
- [102] V. E. Granstaff and S. J. Martin, "Characterization of a thickness-shear mode quartz resonator with multiple nonpiezoelectric layers," *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 75, no. 3, pp. 1319-1329, 1 February 1994.
- [103] M. Valentin and C. Filiâtre, "Application of the impedance transformation on transmission lines to electrochemical microbalance," *Jour. de Physique III*, vol. 4, pp. 1305-1319, July 1994.
- [104] C. Filiâtre, G. Bardèche, and M. Valentin, "Transmission-line model for immersed quartz-crystal sensors," *Sensors and Actuators*, vol. A44, pp. 137-144, 1994.
- [105] A. Ballato and J. R. Vig, "Piezoelectric Devices," in *Encyclopedia of Applied Physics*, G. Trigg, ed., Vol. 14, pp. 129-145. VCH Publishers, New York, 1996.
- [106] T. R. Meeker, "Piezoelectric resonators and applications," in *Encyclopedia of Applied Physics*, G. Trigg, ed., Vol. 14, pp. 147-169, VCH Publishers, New York, 1996.
- [107] R. W. Cernosek, S. J. Martin, A. R. Hillman, and H. L. Bandey, "Comparison of lumped-element and transmission-line models for thickness-shear-mode quartz resonator sensors," *IEEE Intl. Freq. Contr. Symp. Proc.*, pp. 96-104, Orlando, FL, May 1997, and *IEEE Trans. Ultrason., Ferroelect., Freq. Contr.*, vol. 45, no. 5, pp. 1399-1407, September 1998.
- [108] E. Benes, M. Schmid, M. Gröschl, P. Berlinger, H. Nowotny, and K. C. Harms, "Solving the cable problem between crystal sensor and electronics by use of a balanced bridge oscillator circuit," *Proc. Joint Meeting of the 13th European Freq. and Time Forum and the 1999 IEEE Intl. Freq. Control Symp.*, pp. 1023-1026, Besançon, April 1999.
- [109] A. Ballato, "Modeling piezoelectric and piezomagnetic devices and structures via equivalent networks," *IEEE Trans. Ultrason., Ferroelect., Freq. Contr.*, vol. 48, no. 5, pp. 1189-1240, September, 2001. Special Issue on Modeling, Optimization and Design of Surface and Bulk Acoustic Wave Devices.
- [110] A. Arnau, Y. Jiménez, and T. Sogorb, "An extended Butterworth-Van Dyke model for quartz crystal microbalance applications in viscoelastic fluid media," *IEEE Trans. Ultrason., Ferroelect., Freq. Contr.*, vol. 48, no. 5, pp. 1367-1382, September 2001. Special Issue on Modeling, Optimization and Design of Surface and Bulk Acoustic Wave Devices.
- [111] Y. Deblock, P. Campistron, M. Lippert, and C. Bruneel, "Electrical characterization of plate piezoelectric transducers bonded to a finite substrate," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 111, no. 6, pp. 2681-2685, June 2002.
- [112] A. C. Bartlett, "A class of equivalent electrical networks," *Phil. Mag.*, ser. 6, vol. 49, no. 292, pp. 728-739, April 1925.
- [113] A. W. Lawson, "The vibration of piezoelectric plates," *Phys. Rev.*, vol. 62, pp. 71-76, July 1942.
- [114] H. F. Tiersten, "Thickness vibrations of piezoelectric plates," *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 53-58, January 1963.
- [115] G. L. Dybwad, "A sensitive new method for the determination of adhesive bonding between a particle and a substrate," *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 58, no. 7, pp. 2789-2790, 1 October 1985.
- [116] M. Onoe, "Effects of evaporated electrodes on quartz resonator vibrating in a contour mode," *Proc. IRE*, vol. 45, no. 5, p. 694, May 1957.
- [117] L. Dworsky and R. G. Kinsman, "A simple single model for quartz crystal resonator low level drive sensitivity and monolithic filter intermodulation," *IEEE Trans.*

- Ultrason., Ferroelect., Freq. Contr., vol. 41, no. 2, pp. 261-268, March 1994.
- [118] E. P. EerNisse, "An analysis of drive level sensitivity in thickness shear quartz resonators," IEEE Intl. Freq. Control Symp. Proc., pp. 346-356, Honolulu, HI, June, 1996.
- [119] S. -Y. Liu, Y. -H. Kao, Y. O. Su, and T. -P. Perng, "Stresses induced by hydrogen absorption and desorption in Pd nanofilms," J. Alloys and Compounds, vol. 316, pp. 280-283, 2001.
- [120] E. P. EerNisse, E. Benes, and M. Schmid, "The role of localized rotational imbalance in drive level dependence phenomena," these proceedings.
- [121] W. G. Cady, *Piezoelectricity*, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1946; Dover, New York, 1964.
- [122] H. J. Bernstein and V. F. Weisskopf, "About liquids," Am. J. Phys., vol. 55, no. 11, pp. 974-982, November 1987.
- [123] F. Ferrante, A. L. Kipling, and M. Thompson, "Molecular slip at the solid-liquid interface of an acoustic-wave sensor," J. Appl. Phys., vol. 76, no. 6, pp. 3448-3462, 15 September 1994.
- [124] S. Granick, "Soft matter in a tight spot," Physics Today, vol. 52, no. 7, pp. 26-31, July 1999.
- [125] R. Lucklum and G. McHale, "Treatment of slip in a generalized acoustic concept," IEEE Intl. Freq. Contr. Symp. Proc., pp. 40-46, Kansas City, MO, June 2000.
- [126] K. E. Drexler, *Nanosystems: Molecular Machinery, Manufacturing, and Computation*, Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1992. ISBN: 0-471-57518-6.
- [127] Proc. IEEE, vol. 86, no. 8, pp. 1529-1812, August 1998. Special Issue on Integrated Sensors, Microactuators, and Microsystems (MEMS).
- [128] The AMPTIAC Newsletter, Spring 2002, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 1-65. Advanced Materials and Processes Technology Information Analysis Center (AMPTIAC), 201 Mill Street, Rome, NY 13440-6916. Special Issue: Nanotechnology.
- [129] O. Holland and C. Melhuish, "Stigmergy, self-organization, and sorting in collective robotics," Artificial Life, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 173-202, 1999.
- [130] A. Ballato, "Resonant strain levels in modern ceramic plate actuators," In *Am. Ceramic Soc. Trans.: Dielectric Materials*, Vol. 100 (K. M. Nair and A. S. Bhalla, eds.), pp. 443-454, 1999. ISBN 1-57498-066-1.
- [131] A. C. Bartlett, "An extension of a property of artificial lines," Phil. Mag., ser. 7, vol. 4, no. 24, pp. 902-907, November 1927.
- [132] A. C. Bartlett, *The Theory of Electrical Artificial Lines and Filters*, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1930, p. 28.
- [133] O. Brune, "Note on Bartlett's bisection theorem for 4-terminal electrical networks," Phil. Mag., ser. 7, vol. 14, no. 93, pp. 806-811, November 1932.
- [134] J. Hilsenrath, C. W. Beckett, W. S. Benedict, L. Fano, H. L. Hoge, J. F. Masi, R. L. Nuttall, Y. S. Touloukian, and H. W. Woolley, "Tables of Thermal Properties of Gases," NBS Circular 564, National Bureau of Standards, Washington, DC, November 1955.
- [135] J. Hilsenrath, "Thermodynamic Properties of Gases," in *American Institute of Physics Handbook*, 2nd ed., D. E. Gray, Ed., McGraw-Hill, New York, 1963.